

D 3.4 – Modelling tools to evaluate innovative cooling solutions

HighScape - High efficiency, high power density, cost effective, scalable and modular power electronics and control solutions for electric vehicles

HORIZON-CL5-2021-D5-01-02

GA No. 101056824

Work package No.	3
Deliverable No.	D3.4
Expected delivery date	30.6.2025
Actual submission date	04.08.2025
Lead beneficiary	UGent
Dissemination level	PU

**Funded by
the European Union**

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History

Date	Version Number	Comment
05.06.2025	0.1	First draft UGent
17.06.2025	0.2	Experimental results UGent
27.06.2025	0.3	First completed version ready for review and PSB review
04.08.2028	1.0	Review comments incorporated, final version

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Long Version
EV	Electric Vehicle
LTES	Latent Thermal Energy Storage
PCM	Phase Change Material
TES	Thermal Energy Storage

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1 Publishable Executive Summary

As electric vehicles (EVs) become more powerful and compact, keeping their electronic components cool is more important than ever. One of the main challenges is cooling down the SiC MOSFET, which heats up significantly during operation. If not properly managed, this heat can damage the electronics and reduce the vehicle's lifespan.

To address this, a new cooling solution is studied: combining traditional heat sinks with Phase Change Materials (PCMs). These materials absorb a lot of heat as they melt, helping to prevent overheating during short bursts of high power, e.g. during accelerating. Once temperatures cool down, the PCM solidifies and gets ready to absorb heat again. This process is a form of thermal energy storage.

A surrogate model was developed to predict how a PCM-based cooling system behaves. This model uses a network of thermal nodes with thermal resistances and capacitances. It takes into account how heat flows through different parts of the system, including aluminium structures, PCMs, and coolant flow.

To make sure the model was accurate, a lab setup was built that mimics the conditions inside an EV. Heaters simulate the heat from the electronics, and thermocouples track how temperatures change in different parts of the system. The model's predictions closely matched the experimental results, proving the model can reliably forecast how the system performs in real-world scenarios.

By improving the design further, for example by increasing the amount of PCM stored in the heat sink, the PCM heat sink showed even better cooling performance under more realistic power cycles. This approach allows for lighter and more efficient cooling systems, which are vital for the future of electric vehicles.

In short, this deliverable demonstrates that PCMs can provide a smart, compact, and reliable solution to managing heat in EV power electronics, and the modelling tool developed can guide the way to better and faster designs.

2 Introduction

Because of the high heat fluxes generated by the Silicon Carbide (SiC) MOSFETs, effective cooling is required. The maximum allowable junction temperature is around 200°C, beyond this temperature the semiconductor begins to degrade. However, typically it is aimed to stay well below this limit, to ensure the working and lifetime of the device.

2.1 Cooling methods

Various advanced cooling methods for electronic components are proposed in literature, as summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Overview of cooling methods for power electronics components.

Cooling method	Discussion
Heat pipe cooling	Passive devices based on the evaporation and condensation of the working fluid in a sealed tube. Liquid evaporates at the hot end, the vapor travels to the cold end where it condenses. The liquid returns to the hot end by capillary forces.
Two-phase liquid cooling	Working fluid absorbs heat by undergoing a phase change process, often from liquid to vapor.
Direct spray cooling	A liquid is sprayed into fine droplets onto the heated surface. When the droplets impact the surface, they evaporate, removing heat effectively.
Micro heat sink cooling	Heat sinks can be optimized by using very thin channels (order of μm). This increases the surface-to-volume rate drastically, leading to enhanced heat removal.

For the cooling of MOSFETs in EVs, not all cooling methods are suitable. Heat pipe cooling and direct spray cooling both require rather bulky installations. Two-phase cooling requires a separate cooling circuit with complex tubing. Cooling by using a well-designed heat sink can be suitable. However, the heat sink and corresponding cooling circuit need to be designed for maximum heat load. This will result in a heat sink design that is overdimensioned for the majority of the load profile.

This design could be optimized by combining heat sink cooling with temporary heat storage. In this case, the heat sink can be designed for nominal heat load, and the occasional heat flux peaks are covered by the heat storage.

2.2 Thermal energy storage

Thermal energy storage (TES) can be categorized in three types:

- Sensible TES: heat is stored by increasing the temperature of the material (usually liquid or solid) without undergoing a phase change.
- Latent TES: heat is stored while the storage material undergoes a phase change (liquid-solid or liquid-gas).
- Thermochemical TES: energy is stored and released through reversible chemical reactions.

Especially latent TES (LTES) is promising due to its high storage capacity for low volume and small temperature differences. These systems are also less complex compared to thermochemical TES. The

most commonly used phase change process is the liquid-solid phase change. The materials used are often referred to as Phase Change Materials (PCMs).

LTES systems are used for various applications such as the cooling of buildings, LTES for solar heating systems, cold food storage... Another potential application of PCMs lies in the cooling of power electronics, where they act as a thermal buffer to limit peak heat load.

2.3 Design of PCM heat sinks with liquid cooling

Combining LTES with heat sinks for electronics cooling lead to PCM heat sinks, where the PCM acts as thermal buffer. During peak load, the PCM will melt, storing heat and consequently limiting the temperatures seen by the MOSFET. When the peak heat flux is done, the PCM will solidify while gradually releasing its heat.

The design of such heat sinks can be done through Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) Software tools solving the flow and heat transfer equations in 3 dimensions and time. However, numerical methods to model phase change are not fully developed yet and PCM heat sinks require complex geometries complicating the modeling. CFD calculations often require significant computational resources and time. A computationally less expensive option is to use first-order models based on RC (resistor-capacitor) networks. Using this approach, the thermal system is modelled as an electrical analogy. These models allow for rapid simulations for low computational cost. Of course, within these models often assumptions have to be made. Consequently, the local complex phase change behavior cannot be captured in full detail.

Within this project, a RC-model was developed for PCM heat sinks, offering a promising simulation tool for this type of cooling system. Additionally, an experimental setup was designed and commissioned to validate the results of the model.

3 Setup description

Figure 1 gives an overview of the experimental setup built for the model validation. The test section made from aluminum is the central component of the test section. In Figure 2 pictures of this component can be seen. In the three circular holes at the bottom, three cartridge heaters are placed to mimic the thermal behavior of the MOSFET. In the square cavities, PCM is placed as thermal energy storage. The PCM used in the experiments is RT54HC. Table 2 summarizes the properties of the materials. This setups houses 9.9 gram of RT54HC.

Figure 1: Schematic of the test setup.

Figure 2: Picture of the test section: front, bottom, and side view.

Table 2: Material properties.

Property	Aluminium	PCM (RT54HC)
Melting temperature (°C)	NA	50-59 (peak at 54)
Latent heat (J/kg)	NA	200000
Density (kg/m ³)	2710	990 (solid) / 850 (liquid)
Thermal conductivity (W/mK)	175	0.2
Specific heat capacity (J/kgK)	900	2000

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On top of the test section, a water-glycol mixture flows as a coolant. The temperature of the coolant is regulated by a chiller, and the mass flow rate is steered with a three way valve. A mass flow meter enables accurate measurement of the mass flow rate. The inlet and outlet temperature of the coolant are measured with K-type thermocouples.

In the heat sink, eight thermocouples measure the temperature just below the coolant (T_{top}), installed from the bottom. Four thermocouples are placed just above the PCM (T_{mid}) and four just below (T_{bottom}), installed from the side. Figure 3 shows the location of the temperature measurements. For the processing, the average temperature of each level is considered, to eliminate possible non-uniformity effects. All thermocouples are calibrated to an uncertainty of 0.15K.

In Figure 4 a picture of the setup installed in the laboratory is shown.

Figure 3: Indication of temperature measurements in experimental setup.

Figure 4: Picture of the setup in the lab. Thermocouples (green wires) are to be installed. Insulation is removed for visibility.

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An experiment was performed where 150W was applied for one hour with the cartridge heaters, and the inlet temperature of the coolant was regulated at 40°C and a mass flow rate of 5 l/min. Figure 5 shows the temperature measurements in the heat sink. On the left graph, all temperature measurements are reported, on the right side, the average temperature at each section is shown. The biggest temperature variations are seen in the top section, as can be expected as the coolant heats up from inlet to outlet while cooling down the heat sink. The average temperatures will be used to validate the model.

Figure 5: Experimental temperature measurements.

4 Model description

A 2D surrogate model based on fundamental heat transfer theory is developed. The heat sink is simulated as a network of thermal nodes with capacitances, connected through thermal resistances. The model is developed in Python, making use of the fluid database CoolProp.

Figure 6 shows a schematic of the heat sink system, which represents the geometry of the heat sink used in the experimental setup. This geometry will be used to explain the model, and compare it to the experimental results, however, the model allows to vary the dimensions, number of PCM/fins, dimensions of fins, material properties...

Figure 6: Schematic of PCM heat sink: 2D finned geometry.

Figure 7: Different RC-components of the network.

In each node of the network, a heat balance of the following shape is solved:

$$Q_{in,i} = \sum \frac{T_i - T_j}{R_{i,j}} + C_i \frac{dT_i}{dt}$$

The thermal resistance is a function of thickness t , thermal conductivity k and heat transfer area A , and represents the thermal resistance between two nodes i and j . The thermal capacitance of node i is a function of the mass m of the material and specific heat capacity c_p .

$$R_{i,j} = \frac{t_{i,j}}{k_{i,j} \cdot A_{i,j}}$$

$$C_i = m_i \cdot c_{p,i}$$

Below, all different components of the RC network are discussed in more detail.

- At the bottom, the power electronics component (MOSFET) is modelled as a thermal resistance and capacitance. The heat losses generated by the component, are modelled through a heat source Q_{input} , which is given as an input to the model (see Figure 7a). The operation of the MOSFET itself is thus not considered in this model.
- Next, a full layer of aluminum is present to contain the PCM. This is modelled as thermal resistance based on the thickness of the layer, and a thermal capacitance based on the mass and specific heat capacity (Figure 7b). A similar approach is used for aluminum layer 1 and 2.
- For the PCM and fins part, a 2D modelling approach is necessary. In the x-direction, distinction is made between the different materials (aluminum and PCM) and in the y-direction, a discretization is used for accurate modelling of the PCM phase change (in Figure 6 five vertical nodes are shown). Three types of cells occur: wall (dark gray), fin (light gray), or PCM (pink). Each cell is modelled as in Figure 7c, consisting of horizontal and vertical thermal resistances and a thermal capacitance, based on the dimensions of the cell and the material properties. For the PCM cells, the enthalpy method is used to take into account the latent heat of phase change. The enthalpy value of the PCM cell can directly be determined based on the temperature of the cell, by using Figure 8a. From the temperature also the liquid fraction of the PCM can be determined, where 0 represents fully solid state and 1 represents fully liquid.

$$Q_{stored,PCM} = m_{PCM} \frac{dH}{dt} = (m_{PCM} \frac{dH}{dT}) \frac{dT}{dt} = C_{PCM} \frac{dT}{dt}$$

Figure 8: PCM properties (RT54HC): (a) Enthalpy as a function of temperature and (b) liquid fraction as a function of temperature.

- Finally, the behavior of the liquid coolant is modelled through a convective thermal resistance (Figure 7d). The convective heat transfer coefficient h is determined based on the Gnielinski correlation, a widely used approach for turbulent flows. Import to note is that this convection coefficient is dependent on the bulk temperature of the fluid, for which is solved in the system.

$$R_{conv} = \frac{1}{hA}$$

To solve the above described system, all equations are combined in matrix notation and the system is solved as follows:

$$\frac{dT}{dt} = C^{-1} \cdot (Q - G \cdot T)$$

Where C represents a matrix with on the diagonal the thermal capacities of each node, Q contains the input/output heat flows at the PE component and liquid coolant, and G is the conductance matrix containing the thermal resistances.

The system is solved using a scipy solver implemented in python, based on a Runge-Kutta scheme. The output of the model are the temperature evolution over time in each node of the network.

5 Discussion of results

5.1 Verification of the model: single heat pulse

Experimental results and the according results of the model are compared for a case where a heat pulse of 150 W is applied for 60 minutes (Figure 9). In this time, the system is able to reach a steady state. After this pulse, the system reaches a new steady state with zero heat input. Before the start of the experiment, the system is initialized to $\sim 40^{\circ}\text{C}$, which is the temperature of the coolant at the inlet of the heat sink during the experiment. A flow rate of 5 l/min is employed.

The chiller regulates the temperature of the coolant, keeping it constant at 40°C . However, the temperature of the coolant at the inlet of the heat sink is not exactly 40°C over the complete duration of the experiment. Therefore, the measured inlet temperature is used as an input for the model. To this input inlet temperature, a smoothing function was applied to stabilize the model. Figure 10 shows the evolution of the measured inlet temperature and smoothed inlet temperature used by the model. Also the measured outlet temperature and the outlet temperature predicted by the model are reported. Very good agreement can be seen.

Figure 9: Heat input.

Figure 10: Inlet and outlet temperature of the coolant.

Figure 11 shows the temperature evolution measured at different locations in the heat sink during the experiment. It can be seen that the model succeeds very well in predicting the temperature trends. Small deviations between numerical and experimental results are however still present, especially during the transient parts of the test. This probably indicates that the definition of the thermal capacities could still be improved, by using more accurate material properties. Furthermore, the experimental results are also influenced by the heat losses to the environment, which are not accounted for in the model.

Figure 11: Temperature evolution of aluminum at different locations.

Figure 12 presents the evolution of the liquid fraction of the PCM, calculated with the model. It can be seen that the PCM is expected to be completely liquid after 3.6 minutes.

Figure 12: Liquid fraction evolution of PCM (model).

The above results show that the model can successfully predict temperature trends in a PCM heat sink. However, as only a limited amount of PCM is present in the heat sink, PCM effects are small and difficult to detect. Experiments with a different geometry could lead to additional insights into the model validation.

5.2 Further application of the model

Section 5.1 showed how the model is able to predict the behavior of a PCM heat sink. Nevertheless, the geometry used in the experimental setup has definitely possibilities for improvements. Therefore, extra calculations are performed that show better working of a PCM heat sink and its working under a more realistic heat input profile.

The PCM heat sink has the same outer dimensions as the one before, however, now ten PCM/fin divisions are made instead of three and the aluminum layers (0, 1 and 2) are made thinner, enabling more space to store PCM within the heat sink. In total, now 50 grams of RT54HC is placed in the heat sink. The coolant inlet temperature is kept constant at 40°C and the coolant has a mass flow rate of 5 l/min. Figure 13 shows the heat profile applied.

Figure 13: Applied heat input into the system.

Figure 14 shows the temperature and PCM liquid fraction evolution over time, under the varying heat flux. On these figures, the heat flux is applied to the bottom, and the cooling is present at the top. It can be seen that at first, during the first two minutes, the system is increasing and decreasing in temperature under the high input peaks. The PCM is heating up slower due to its low thermal conductivity. Once the PCM reaches the melting temperature, it starts storing energy through its latent heat. After four minutes, the system is cooling down as no heat input is present anymore. It can be seen that at this point, the PCM is gradually releasing its stored heat, while solidifying.

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Figure 14: Temperature and liquid fraction evolution of the system over time.

6 Conclusion

The primary objective of this work was to develop a computationally efficient and physically accurate surrogate modelling tool for simulating the thermal behavior of PCM-based heat sinks used in the cooling of SiC MOSFETs in power electronic systems. A two-dimensional RC network model was created to represent the complex heat transfer processes, including latent heat storage in the PCM, conductive paths in the aluminum structure, and convective cooling from the liquid coolant.

The model was implemented in Python and incorporates temperature-dependent thermal properties as well as the enthalpy method to simulate phase change phenomena. Validation was performed through a dedicated experimental setup, which closely replicated the operational environment of a PCM heat sink. The comparison between measured data and model predictions showed good agreement, indicating that the model reliably captures key thermal dynamics of the system.

Although some deviations were observed—particularly during transient heating and cooling phases—these are likely attributable to simplified assumptions regarding heat losses and material properties. Despite these limitations, the model proved capable of accurately predicting the evolution of temperature and PCM liquid fraction over time, thereby fulfilling its intended role as a design and analysis tool.

In summary, a validated surrogate model has been successfully developed, offering a fast and effective approach for evaluating PCM-based thermal management strategies in power electronic applications.

6.1 Deviations, Impact and Recovery Actions

There are no deviations, impact and recovery actions regarding this deliverable.